

An apparent quantitative relation between Newton's law of universal gravitation and Coulomb's law derived from a geometry-based hypothetical system

Zhe Lu

September 30, 2022

Abstract. In a previously derived geometry-based energetic expression, the Newtonian gravitational constant (G) is apparently related to the Planck constant (h) such that the accepted value of G can be calculated from that of h . Here, based on that expression, the relation between Newton's law of universal gravitation and Coulomb's law is evaluated. This evaluation in turn yields the apparent relation between G and the Coulomb constant (k_e) that

$\frac{G}{k_e} = \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{m}{s}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg \ m^2}\right] \left(\frac{C}{kg}\right)^2$ and, furthermore, the apparent relation that $c = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi G q_e^2} \left[h \times 10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h^2 \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg \ m^2}\right] \left(\frac{m \ C}{s \ kg}\right)^2$, in which c is the speed of light in vacuum, q_e is the elementary charge with the unit C , α is the fine-structure constant, and φ is the geometric-constant golden-ratio. In terms of h , the latter relation is a quadratic equation. One solution of this equation is, as expected, the accepted Planck constant itself whereas the other solution has the significant digits of G . Furthermore, from the relation, the gravitational potential energy could be expressed in two mutually nonexclusive forms in terms of temporal and spatial frequencies, or in terms of curvature.

Introduction

Newton's law of universal gravitation quantifies the gravitational force (F_G) between the masses (M_1 and M_2) of two objects with a distance of r between their centers of mass in a form of

$$F_G = G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r^2} \quad (1)$$

where G is the Newtonian constant of gravitation [1,2]. Derived from this law, the gravitational potential energy (U_G) between M_1 and M_2 is expressed as

$$U_G = -G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r} \quad (2)$$

with a customary negative sign. In Einstein's general theory of relativity, the cause of gravity is interpreted in items of geometry as the curvature of space-time.

Coulomb's law quantifies the electrostatic force (F_e) between two interacting charges Q_1 and Q_2 separated over a distance of r , in a form analogous to that of Newton's law of universal gravitation:

$$F_e = k_e \frac{Q_1 Q_2}{r^2} \quad (3)$$

where the Coulomb constant k_e is given by

$$k_e = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \quad (4)$$

in which ϵ_0 is the electric constant. Derived from Coulomb's law, the electric potential energy (U_e) between Q_1 and Q_2 is expressed as

$$U_e = k_e \frac{Q_1 Q_2}{r}. \quad (5)$$

The strength of the electromagnetic interaction between elementary charged particles is quantified by the fine-structure constant (α). Many equivalent expressions of α in terms of other physical constants include

$$\alpha = \frac{q_e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar c} = \frac{q_e^2}{2\epsilon_0\hbar c} = \left(\frac{q_e}{q_p}\right)^2 = \frac{k_e q_e^2}{\hbar c} = \frac{2\pi k_e q_e^2}{\hbar c} \quad (6)$$

where h is the Planck constant related to its reduced form $\hbar$ by 2π , lowercase letter c denotes the speed of light in vacuum, q_e is the elementary charge, and q_p is the Planck charge. For later use, the final version of the expression in Eq. 6 is rewritten as

$$k_e = \frac{\alpha\hbar c}{2\pi q_e^2}. \quad (7)$$

According to Einstein's mass-energy relation, c relates mass (M) to energy (E) such that

$$E = Mc^2. \quad (8)$$

In the Planck relation, the electromagnetic energy carried by a photon is expressed as

$$E_h = h\nu. \quad (9)$$

where ν is the ordinary temporal frequency of the photon. The Boltzmann entropy (S) was expressed by Planck in a form of

$$S = k_B \ln W \quad (10)$$

related to energy at a given absolute temperature T in the unit K as

$$E_{k_B} = k_B T \ln W \quad (11)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and W is the so-called thermodynamic probability.

In this summary of a third piece of self-assigned homework, an evaluation of the relative strength between gravitational potential energy and electric potential energy is described. The summaries of other two related pieces have already been shared. In one previous summary, relations among the physical constants G , h and k_B in different physical-unit systems are evaluated [3], whereas in another summary and its updated version [4,5], the following relation is described:

$$\frac{1}{2}(G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}) = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} J = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi J \quad (12)$$

in which:

i. the inverse of the well-known geometric-constant gold-ratio φ is defined as

$$\frac{1}{\varphi} = \frac{-1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2} \quad (13)$$

the value of whose positive solution, i.e., 0.618..., is adopted;

ii. the relation

$$-\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = -k_B T \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} J = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi J \quad (14)$$

defines the distribution of energy of an asymmetrically partitioned system;

iii. the asymmetric partition is specified by

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = 1 \quad (15)$$

such that a probability space is partitioned according to a ratio of φ into two portions given by $\frac{1}{\varphi}$ and $\frac{1}{\varphi^2}$;

iv. as shown in Eq. 14, the latter two parts of Eq. 12 contain the hidden thermodynamic β in its inverse form, which is usually taken as $k_B T$ and would be explicitly expressed there as

$$\frac{1}{\beta} = k_B T = 1 J; \quad (16)$$

Furthermore, using the following rearranged form of Eq. 12

$$G = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2} - h \times 10^{23} \text{ kg}^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1} \quad (17)$$

all six accepted significant digits of G , i.e., $6.67430 (\times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2})$ [1,2], can be calculated from those of h that has an exact value with zero uncertainty [1,6]. Furthermore, when calculated with all nine significant digits of h , the resulting G value is $6.67429758 \times 10^{-11} (\text{kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2})$.

Evaluation of a hypothetical system

Both the gravitational potential energy and the electric potential energy are specified in accordance with Eqs. 2 and 5, with each physical quantity being assigned an implicit unity value such that

$$U_G = -G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r} = -G \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (18)$$

and

$$U_e = k_e \frac{Q_1^+ Q_2^-}{r} = -k_e \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (19)$$

where Q_1^+ and Q_2^- denote a positive charge and a negative charge, respectively, whereas uppercase letter C denotes the charge unit coulomb. The ratio of U_G to U_e is expressed as

$$\frac{U_G}{U_e} = \frac{-G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r}}{k_e \frac{Q_1^+ Q_2^-}{r}} = \frac{G \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}}{k_e \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}} \quad (20)$$

Combining Eq. 8, 17 and 20 yields

$$\frac{U_G}{U_e} = \frac{G \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}}{k_e \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}} = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} - h \times 10^{23} \text{ s}^{-1}}{x M c^2} \quad (21)$$

where $x M c^2$ is the equivalent amount of all additional energy required to establish the relation;

$$x = 10^{-7} \quad (22)$$

which can be either directly calculated or reached on the basis of the following relation between k_e and c^2 :

$$k_e = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} = \frac{c^2 \mu_0}{4\pi} = c^2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg m C}^{-2} \quad (23)$$

where μ_0 is the magnetic constant.

Substituting Eq. 22 into Eq. 21 gives

$$\frac{G \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}}{k_e \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}} = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} - h \times 10^{23} \text{ s}^{-1}}{10^{-7} c^2 \text{ kg}} \quad (24)$$

reformatted to

$$\frac{G \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}}{k_e \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}} = \left(\frac{1}{c} \text{ m s}^{-1}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}\right]. \quad (25)$$

The left side of Eq. 25 can be written in terms of the magnitude of force as

$$\frac{G \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}}{k_e \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}} = \left(\frac{1}{c} \text{ m s}^{-1}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}\right]. \quad (26)$$

Eq. 26 apparently relates Newton's law of universal gravitation to Coulomb's law. The unit of velocity, which multiplies $\frac{1}{c}$, may be explicitly denoted as u_v such that

$$\frac{G \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}}{k_e \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}} = \left(\frac{u_v}{c}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}\right] \quad (27)$$

where

$$u_v = \frac{m}{s}. \quad (28)$$

Below, $\frac{m}{s}$ may be thought as u_v . Both Eqs. 25 and 26 are simplified to

$$\frac{G}{k_e} = \left(\frac{1 m}{c s}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg m^2}\right] \left(\frac{c}{kg}\right)^2 \quad (29)$$

or

$$G = \left(\frac{1 m}{c s}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg m^2}\right] \left(\frac{c}{kg}\right)^2 k_e \quad (30)$$

which relates G to k_e . In this hypothetical system, the amount of electric potential energy both reflects and can be used to determine that of the gravitational potential energy and *vice versa*.

Substituting Eq. 4 into Eq. 30 gives

$$G = \left(\frac{1 m}{c s}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg m^2}\right] \left(\frac{c}{kg}\right)^2 \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0}. \quad (31)$$

Eqs. 30 and 31 may be sequentially written compactly as

$$G = \zeta_{(G/k_e)} k_e = \frac{\zeta_{(G/k_e)}}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \quad (32)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{(G/k_e)} &= \frac{G}{k_e} \\ &= \left(\frac{1 m}{c s}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg m^2}\right] \left(\frac{c}{kg}\right)^2 \\ &= \frac{(1.330036773 - 0.662607015) \times 10^{-3} c^2}{(2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2} \frac{c^2}{kg^2} = 7.42615758 \times 10^{-21} \frac{c^2}{kg^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Note that the values of c and h underlying $\zeta_{(G/k_e)}$ are exact [1,6,7]. (The letter ζ is chosen for its relatively less frequent use in physics.)

Moreover, substituting Eq. 7 into Eq. 29 yields

$$\frac{G}{\frac{ahc}{2\pi q_e^2}} = \left(\frac{1 m}{c s}\right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg m^2}\right] \left(\frac{c}{kg}\right)^2 \quad (34)$$

simplified to

$$\frac{2\pi G c q_e^2}{ah} = \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg m^2}\right] \left(\frac{m c}{s kg}\right)^2 \quad (35)$$

which exhibits a relation among the following three sets of constants and units: **i.** five explicitly expressed physical constants c , G , h , q_e and α ; **ii.** four explicitly expressed physical units kg , m ,

s and C ; and **iii.** five mathematical constants 1, 2, π , φ and e (the base of natural logarithm). In addition, as mentioned above, there is the hidden constant k_B and the associated unit K of T (Eqs. 12, 14 and 16).

Eq. 35, may be rewritten as

$$Gc = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi q_e^2} \left[h \times 10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 - h^2 \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2} \right] \left(\frac{m \cdot C}{s \cdot kg} \right)^2 \quad (36)$$

Then, the speed light in vacuum may be expressed in the form of a compound constant:

$$c = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi G q_e^2} \left[h \times 10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 - h^2 \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2} \right] \left(\frac{m \cdot C}{s \cdot kg} \right)^2 \quad (37)$$

For further illustration, Eqs. 29 and 35 are reformatted to

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{Gc^2}{k_e} \times 10^3 \frac{s^2 \cdot kg^2}{m^2 \cdot C^2} + h \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2} \right) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi = - \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \quad (38)$$

and

$$\frac{\pi G c q_e^2}{\alpha h} \times 10^3 \frac{s^2 \cdot kg^2}{m^2 \cdot C^2} + \frac{h}{2} \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi = - \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i}. \quad (39)$$

The latter part in Eq. 38 or 39 expresses the sum of weighted natural logarithmic probabilities of the two portions of a probability space partitioned in accordance with Eq. 15.

Discussion

In terms of h , Eq. 37 is a quadratic equation, which may be put into the standard form

$$10^{30} \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2} h^2 - 10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 h + \frac{2\pi G c q_e^2}{\alpha} \left(\frac{s \cdot kg}{m \cdot C} \right)^2 = 0 \quad (40)$$

whose two solutions are given by

$$h = \frac{10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 \pm \sqrt{\left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 \right]^2 - \left(\frac{8\pi G c q_e^2}{\alpha} \right) \times 10^{30} \frac{kg s^3}{m^4 C^2}}}{2 \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2}} \quad (41)$$

The solution with a smaller value is the accepted Planck constant itself:

$$h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \frac{kg \cdot m^2}{s} \quad (42)$$

whereas the hypothetical, formulaic solution with a larger value, denoted as h' , may be expressed and calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
h' &= \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 \times 10^{-33} \frac{kg \, m^2}{s} - h \right] \\
&= (1.330036773 - 0.662607015) \times 10^{-33} \frac{kg \, m^2}{s} = 6.67429758 \times 10^{-34} \frac{kg \, m^2}{s} \quad (43)
\end{aligned}$$

whose significant digits would be the same as those of the accepted G , if they were round to the sixth significant digit [4,5]. The mathematical validity of the two solutions may be readily checked numerically using Eq. 41.

From Eqs. 7, 20, and 24, the gravitational potential energy $G \frac{kg^2}{m}$ in the present hypothetical system might be expressed in the following manner:

$$-U_G = G \frac{kg^2}{m} = 10^{30} \left(\frac{c}{q_e} \right)^2 \alpha \left(\frac{1 \, m}{c \, s} \right) \left[10^{-33} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 \frac{kg \, m^2}{s} - h \right] \left(\frac{s}{kg \, m^2} \right) \left(\frac{h}{2\pi} \right) \left(\frac{1}{s} \right) \quad (44)$$

where, for clarity, some extra parentheses are used. Regardless of whether h itself is used or it is substituted by the other solution h' , the product $\left[10^{-33} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 \frac{kg \, m^2}{s} - h \right] h$ in Eq. 44 always returns a product of h and h' :

$$\begin{aligned}
\left[10^{-33} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 \frac{kg \, m^2}{s} - h \right] h &= h' h = h h' \\
&= 6.62607015 \times 6.67429758 \times 10^{-68} \, J^2 s^2 \\
&= 4.42243640 \times 10^{-67} \, J^2 s^2 \quad (45)
\end{aligned}$$

As such, Eq. 44 could be rewritten as

$$-U_G = G \frac{kg^2}{m} = 10^{30} \left(\frac{c}{q_e} \right)^2 \alpha \left(\frac{1 \, m}{c \, s} \right) \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(h' h \frac{s}{kg \, m^2} \right) \frac{1}{s} \quad (46)$$

This expression may be considered in the following two mutually nonexclusive ways among other possible ones.

First, if Eq. 46 were considered in the framework of the Planck relation in terms of the reduced Planck constant, the series of five multiplying unit-less components, $10^{30} \times \left(\frac{c}{q_e} \right)^2 \times \alpha \times \left(\frac{1 \, m}{c \, s} \right) \times \left(h' h \frac{s}{kg \, m^2} \right)$, should in principle be the product of the number of pocket of energy and the value of temporal angular frequency (ω). To get an initial sense of the level of energy concerned here, the amount of gravitational potential energy is normalized against $\left(\frac{c}{q_e} \right)^2$, i.e., the number of interacting pair of elementary charges q_e^2 per pair of charges C^2 . As such, Eq. 46 is rewritten as

$$\frac{-U_G}{\left(\frac{c}{q_e}\right)^2} = \frac{G \frac{kg^2}{m}}{\left(\frac{c}{q_e}\right)^2} = \frac{h}{2\pi} \omega \quad (47)$$

The quantity $\left(\frac{c}{q_e}\right)^2$ might also be viewed as the ratio of the energy between two interacting charges defined by $k_e \frac{c^2}{r}$ to that between two interacting elementary charges defined by $k_e \frac{q_e^2}{r}$, in which r should be the same for both cases. In Eq. 47, the normalized amount of gravitational potential energy would then be viewed as a product of $\frac{h}{2\pi}$ and ω in the unit $\frac{1}{s}$, and calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-U_G}{\left(\frac{c}{q_e}\right)^2} &= \frac{G \frac{kg^2}{m}}{\left(\frac{c}{q_e}\right)^2} = \frac{h}{2\pi} \omega = \frac{h}{2\pi} \times 10^{30} \alpha \left(\frac{1 m}{c s}\right) \left(h' \frac{s}{kg m^2}\right) \frac{1}{s} \\ &= \frac{6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \times 10^{30} \times 7.2973525693 \times 10^{-3} \times 6.67429758 \times 10^{-34}}{2 \times 3.14159265 \times 2.99792458 \times 10^8} J \\ &= 1.71327215 \times 10^{-48} J \\ &= \frac{1.71327215 \times 10^{-48} J}{1.602176634 \times 10^{-19} J} eV = 1.06934037 \times 10^{-29} eV \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

For reference, the estimated upper limit of the energy of a graviton, a particle of energy hypothesized by Blokhintsev and Gal'perin, is on the order of as low as $10^{-29} eV$ [8-11] or even $10^{-30} eV$ [12,13]. Thus far, gravitational waves, but not gravitons, have been detected [14].

The temporal angular frequency ω in Eq. 48 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &= 10^{30} \alpha \left(\frac{1 m}{c s}\right) \left(h' \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2}\right) \frac{1}{s} \\ &= \frac{10^{30} \times 7.2973525693 \times 10^{-3} \times 6.67429758 \times 10^{-34}}{2.99792458 \times 10^8} \frac{1}{s} = 1.62461401 \times 10^{-14} \frac{1}{s}. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

The wavelength (λ) corresponding to this ω , denoted as λ_ω , would be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_\omega &= \frac{2\pi c}{\omega} = \frac{2\pi c^2}{h' \alpha} \times 10^{-30} kg m s \\ &= \frac{2 \times 3.14159265 \times (2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2 \times 10^{-30}}{6.67429758 \times 10^{-34} \times 7.2973525693 \times 10^{-3}} m \\ &= 1.15944560 \times 10^{23} m. \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

Second, the presence of $\frac{uv}{c}$, i.e., $\left(\frac{1 m}{c s}\right)$, in Eq. 46 suggests an alternative expression in terms of spatial angular frequency, denoted here by k . Using Eq. 46 as an example to illustrate this possibility, it is reformatted to

$$\frac{-U_G}{\left(\frac{c}{q_e}\right)^2} = \frac{G \frac{kg^2}{m}}{\left(\frac{c}{q_e}\right)^2} = \frac{h' m}{2\pi s} \times 10^{30} \alpha \left(h \frac{s}{kg m^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{1}{s} \right) = \frac{\check{G}'}{2\pi} k \quad (51)$$

in which $\frac{m}{s}$ would convert the units $\frac{kg m^2}{s}$ (i.e., $J s$) of $\frac{h'}{2\pi}$ to the units $\frac{kg m^3}{s^2}$ (i.e., $J m$) of a converting factor $\left(\frac{\check{G}'}{2\pi}\right)$, and $\frac{1}{c}$ would convert ω in the unit $\frac{1}{s}$ to k in the unit $\frac{1}{m}$. As such, the final expression in Eq. 51 is a succinct product between $\frac{\check{G}'}{2\pi}$ and k , in which

$$\frac{\check{G}'}{2\pi} = \frac{h' m}{2\pi s} = \frac{6.67429758 \times 10^{-34}}{2 \times 3.14159265} J m = 1.06224745 \times 10^{-34} J m \quad (52)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} k &= 10^{30} \alpha \left(h \frac{s}{kg m^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{1}{s} \right) \\ &= \frac{10^{30} \times 7.2973525693 \times 10^{-3} \times 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}}{2.99792458 \times 10^8} \frac{1}{m} = 1.61287480 \times 10^{-14} \frac{1}{m}. \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

The formulaic wavelength corresponding to this spatial angular frequency k , denoted as λ_κ , would be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_\kappa &= \frac{2\pi}{k} = \frac{2\pi c}{h\alpha} \times 10^{-30} kg m^2 \\ &= \frac{2 \times 3.14159265 \times 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \times 10^{-30}}{6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \times 7.2973525693 \times 10^{-3}} m = 3.89564355 \times 10^{14} m. \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

For reference, a light year equals $9.461 \times 10^{15} m$.

In either above consideration, purely on a numerical ground, the roles of h and h' might be swapped. As a result, there would be two sets of possible converting factors, h or h' and $\check{G}'$ or $\check{G}$, in the absence of any exclusion.

To calculate a reference level of energy primarily on the basis of c , h , and $\check{G}$, Eq. 46 is rewritten to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-U_G}{10^{30} \left(\frac{c}{q_e}\right)^2} \alpha &= \frac{G \frac{kg^2}{m}}{10^{30} \left(\frac{c}{q_p}\right)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \right) h' h \frac{m}{s} \left(\frac{s}{kg m^2} \right) \frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{1}{s} \right) \\ &= \frac{h}{2\pi} \left[\left(h' \frac{s}{kg m^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{m}{s} \right) \left(\frac{1}{s} \right) \right] = \frac{h}{2\pi} \omega^s \\ &= \frac{h' m}{2\pi s} \left[\left(h \frac{s}{kg m^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{1}{s} \right) \right] = \frac{\check{G}'}{2\pi} k^s \\ &= \frac{6.67429758 \times 10^{-34} \times 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}}{2 \times 3.14159265 \times 2.99792458 \times 10^8} J = 2.34456526 \times 10^{-76} J \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{2.34456526 \times 10^{-76} \text{ J}}{1.602176634 \times 10^{-19} \text{ J}} eV = 1.46336253 \times 10^{-57} eV. \quad (55)$$

Consequently, the amount of gravitational potential energy is normalized against $10^{30} \left(\frac{C}{q_p}\right)^2$, i.e., 10^{30} times the number of interacting Planck-charge-pair q_p^2 per C^2 . In Eq. 55, the normalized amount of gravitational potential energy might be viewed as a product of $\frac{h}{2\pi}$ and ω^s or that of $\frac{\check{g}'}{2\pi}$ and k^s , where the superscript s indicates that here, ω^s and k^s are the respective scalable reference levels of ω and κ . The temporal angular frequency would be calculated as

$$\omega^s = \left(h' \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2}\right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ m}}{c \text{ s}}\right) \left(\frac{1}{s}\right) = \frac{6.67429758 \times 10^{-34}}{2.99792458 \times 10^8} = 2.22630603 \times 10^{-42} \frac{1}{s}. \quad (56)$$

The wavelength corresponds to this temporal angular frequency ω^s might then be calculated as

$$\lambda_{\omega}^s = \frac{2\pi c}{\omega^s} = \frac{2\pi c^2}{h'} kg \cdot m \cdot s = \frac{2 \times 3.14159265 \times (2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2}{6.67429758 \times 10^{-34}} m = 8.46088336 \times 10^{50} m \quad (57)$$

In contrast, the spatial angular frequency and its corresponding formulaic wavelength are calculated as

$$k^s = \left(h \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2}\right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ s}}{c \text{ m}}\right) = \frac{6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}}{2.99792458 \times 10^8} \frac{1}{m} = 2.21021909 \times 10^{-42} \frac{1}{m} \quad (58)$$

and

$$\lambda_{\kappa}^s = \frac{2\pi}{k^s} = \frac{2\pi c}{h} kg \cdot m^2 = \frac{2 \times 3.14159265 \times 2.99792458 \times 10^8}{6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}} m = 2.84278845 \times 10^{42} m \quad (59)$$

much longer than a light year ($9.461 \times 10^{15} m$).

Conceptually, k and ω might be considered in terms of not just frequencies but also curvature. The curvature (κ) of a differentiable curve can be defined using the osculating circle. As such, κ is a function of the inverse of the radius R :

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{R} \quad (60)$$

Then, in terms of length dimension alone, the unit of curvature of a curve would be $\frac{1}{m}$, whereas in terms of time dimension alone, it would be $\frac{1}{s}$. Furthermore, in differential geometry, the Gaussian curvature of a surface at a given point, here denoted as κ_s , is the product of the two principle curvatures κ_1 and κ_2 at that point:

$$\kappa_s = \kappa_1 \kappa_2 \quad (61)$$

For a sphere of radius R , the Gaussian curvature is given by

$$\kappa_s = \frac{1}{R^2} \quad (62)$$

As a further exercise, Eq. 44 is reformatted as

$$-U_G = G \frac{kg^2}{m} = 10^{30} \alpha \left(\frac{c}{q_e} \right)^2 \left[10^{-33} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\phi^2} \right) \ln \phi^2 m - h \frac{s}{kg m} \right] \frac{h}{2\pi c} \left(\frac{1}{s^2} \right) \quad (63)$$

or

$$-U_G = G \frac{kg^2}{m} = 10^{30} \alpha \left(\frac{c}{q_e} \right)^2 \left[10^{-33} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\phi^2} \right) \ln \phi^2 m - h \frac{s}{kg m} \right] \frac{h}{2\pi} \left(\frac{1}{c s^2} \right) \quad (64)$$

which can be scaled to a specific amount of energy. In both expressions of $-U_G$, the multiplying component of $10^{30} \alpha \left(\frac{c}{q_e} \right)^2$ is overall unit-less. However, in Eq. 63, the multiplying component $\left[10^{-33} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\phi^2} \right) \ln \phi^2 m - h \frac{s}{kg m} \right] \frac{h}{2\pi c}$ has the net units $J s^2$, and would relate the units $\frac{1}{s^2}$ to $-U_G$. By contrast, in Eq. 64, the multiplying component $\left[10^{-33} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\phi^2} \right) \ln \phi^2 m - h \frac{s}{kg m} \right] \frac{h}{2\pi}$ has the net units $J m s$, whereas the component $\frac{1}{c s^2}$ has the net units $\frac{1}{m s}$ because c converts one of the two multiplying time units in s to a length unit in m . Thus, the former component in the units $J m s$ would relate the latter component in the units $\frac{1}{m s}$ to the gravitational potential energy in the unit J .

References

1. Tiesinga, E., Mohr, P.J., Newell, D.B. and Taylor, B.N. CODATA recommended values of the fundamental constants: 2018. *Review of Modern Physics* 93: 025010-1-63, 2021.
2. 2018 CODATA Value: Newtonian constant of gravitation. *The NIST Reference on Constants, Units, and Uncertainty*. NIST. Retrieved on September 27, 2022. <https://www.physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?bg>
3. Lu, Z. Apparent relations between the physical constants G, h and k and physical units. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6654172>, 2022.
4. Lu, Z. An apparent relation between the Newtonian gravitational constant and the Planck constant in a geometry-based energetic expression derived from a hypothetical system. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6555072>, 2022 (1st version).
5. Lu, Z. An apparent relation between the Newtonian gravitational constant and the Planck constant in a geometry-based energetic expression derived from a hypothetical system. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7126702>, 2022 (2nd version).
6. 2018 CODATA Value: Planck constant. *The NIST Reference on Constants, Units, and Uncertainty*. NIST. Retrieved on September 27, 2022. https://www.physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?h|search_for=h
7. 2018 CODATA Value: Speed of light in vacuum. *The NIST Reference on Constants, Units, and Uncertainty*. NIST. Retrieved on September 27, 2022. <https://physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?c>
8. Goldhaber, A.S., and Nieto, M.M. Mass of the graviton. *Physical Review D* 9, 1119–1121, 1974. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.9.1119>.
9. Desai, S. Limit on graviton mass from galaxy cluster Abell 1689. *Physics Letter B* 778, 325–331, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physletb.2018.01.052>. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0370269318300601>.
10. Gupta, S., and Desai, S., 2019. Bound on the graviton mass from Chandra X-ray cluster sample. *Classical and Quantum Gravity* 36 (10), 105001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6382/ab1599>.
11. Piórkowska-Kurpas, A, Cao, S. and Marek Biesiada. Graviton mass from X-COP galaxy clusters. *Journal of High Energy Astrophysics* 33: 37-43, 2022.
12. Gupta, S., and Desai, S. Limit on graviton mass using stacked galaxy cluster catalogs from SPT-SZ, Planck-SZ and SDSS-redMaPPer. *Annals of Physics* 399, 85–92, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aop.2018.09.017>.
13. Rana, A., Jain, D., Mahajan, S., and Mukherjee, A. Bounds on graviton mass using weak lensing and SZ effect in galaxy clusters. *Physics Letter B* 781, 220–226, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physletb.2018.03.076>.
14. Abbott et al. Observation of gravitational waves from a binary black hole merger. *Physical Review Letters* 116: 061102, 1-16.